

DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES CHANGING THE WORLD

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A review of the main areas of digital transformation that a business that wants to remain competitive cannot ignore.

The phrase "digital transformation" has become more and more common. It seems that new digital technologies that are actively developing on a global scale will soon change our understanding of IT capabilities.

One of the key technologies on which digital information is based is the Internet of Things. The fact that many household appliances are connected to the power grid is commonplace, but gradually, more and more objects of the physical world are connected to the Internet, which allows for the collection of information and even remote control of these objects. In fact, a virtual copy of a physical object appears on the Internet, containing various parameters of the object and the outside world, and allowing the object to be controlled via the Internet.

An example of the Internet of Things is a device, such as a projector in a movie theater, which sends a signal to the technical support service about a detected malfunction and a list of spare parts that need to be replaced as part of an unscheduled repair.

The next stage of the development of the Internet of Things is the interaction of things not only with people, but also with each other, which will allow for automated interaction on conveyor lines, in systems for technical repair and maintenance of equipment, in logistics and many other areas of business. There are also issues that still need to be resolved: the creation of electronics with minimal power consumption, as well as the creation of new communication standards for the interaction of things with each other.

The most promising technology is augmented reality, which allows adding objects from the virtual world to the real world. Imagine that while walking down the street you will see additional information about objects and people around you. Examples of augmented reality already exist and are actively used; in some Moscow parks you can already see tags showing the bindings of an object in the physical world to the virtual world. Games with elements of augmented reality are actively spreading, there are virtual mirrors and fitting rooms in stores selling clothes, augmented reality is already being tested in cars. At the same time, there are still issues to be resolved on the path to the active

use of augmented reality technologies. For example, the accuracy of geolocation tools is still insufficient, or computer vision technologies are imperfect for binding objects of the physical world to their virtual copies. However, it is safe to say that in the near future this technology can clearly be considered a breakthrough.

The emergence of technical devices that allow a person to be in virtual reality has made this technology in demand in the entertainment industry. Virtual reality helmets and suits, specialized rooms, allow you to get into an unknown world that is programmed so that all your actions cause a response from the virtual world, which allows you to immerse yourself in it 100%.

In business, virtual reality technologies are not so actively used, rather, 3D modeling technologies are now in demand there. Examples of building digital 3D models of real-world objects are construction companies, manufacturers of complex technological products, oil production, and other industries.

Within the framework of 3D modeling, we can talk not only about building models of objects, but also filling them with data, which in turn allows you to optimize the processes of making management decisions and subsequently link the means of designing products with the means of their production.

At the same time, on the way to the mass introduction of virtual reality technologies, it will still be necessary to increase the realism of the display of the virtual world in new versions of devices that will provide an even more realistic presence of a person in virtual reality.

Machine learning and artificial intelligence technologies are also experiencing a rise. It can be seen that most of the largest IT companies are actively buying up young technology companies that deal with these technologies. In fact, several ecosystems are currently being formed around which services based on artificial intelligence will be created.

Translation from language to language, speech recognition, algorithms for finding the right solutions - all this has made it possible to achieve the emergence of computers with elements of artificial intelligence, which in some areas is already stronger than a person. One example of the spread of artificial intelligence technologies is the active promotion of the Watson service by IBM, which shows miracles not only in playing chess and Go, but also in making medical diagnoses, as well as in other areas of human activity, where the use of computers was previously unthinkable.

A driver, a journalist, a lawyer, a doctor - all these specialties can already be replaced by artificial intelligence. And although there are still many unresolved

issues on the path of developing artificial intelligence technologies, in the next five to seven years we will see an explosive growth in achievements in this area.

The presence of robots in human life has been discussed by science fiction writers more than once, but now robots are already coming into our reality. Replacing simple functions performed by people in production allows us to reduce the number of errors, as well as speed up their execution.

It is no secret that many industrial companies actively use robotics in assembly lines and logistics, which allows us to reduce the human factor and get by with minimal involvement of people.

Reducing the cost of industrial robots allows us to achieve economic efficiency from their use, and in fact, people only have to watch how the mechanisms automatically produce products without human intervention.

In Germany, the term Industry 4.0 has even appeared, which implies the construction of fully automated production and logistics networks, where machines interact with each other within the production process. The combination of robotics, the Internet of Things, artificial intelligence and 3D printing already now allows us to build fully mechanized factories for the production of products, from sneakers to cars.

Another technology that can change the construction industry and mechanical engineering. The creation of a huge number of 3D printers that can print products from polymers, concrete, metals and even gold changes the very understanding of the production cycle, because many of the products can be obtained at home, having only a three-dimensional model and a 3D printer.

There are already examples of printing entire houses using specialized 3D printers, and printing bridges is on the way. There is even an example of a bus completely printed on a 3D printer.

Mechanical engineering has already actively joined the development of 3D printing, where some parts are cheaper to print than to obtain using "classic" methods. Clothing and shoe designers are already printing their new products. Builders, jewelers, doctors, they are all already actively using 3D printing in their business processes. A printer has already been created that can print itself, and Chinese companies have begun to produce construction kits from which anyone can assemble a 3D printer at home. And although the technology still faces issues related to printing complex composite products, it is quite possible that it will soon be possible to print new sneakers for yourself that take into account the features of your foot as much as possible. And do it without leaving your home.

The combined use of innovative digital technologies allows not only to change a particular business process, but to completely restructure the industry, introducing a product that did not exist before. The most fascinating thing about digital transformation is the ability to use all these technologies together.

The Internet of Things allows you to combine the virtual world with the real one, artificial intelligence based on huge amounts of data obtained from the Internet of Things will be able to form conclusions and decisions. Augmented and virtual reality will make the new world visible to humans. And robotics and 3D printing will automate most routine operations.

We can say that the emergence of many breakthrough technologies will change people's lives, destroy several old ones and create many new professions and will certainly make the world digital. Such digitalization of the world will lead to changes in all industries, and most importantly, many new companies will appear, while the leaders will be those who can not only stay on the wave of digital transformation, but also lead it.

Specialists develop technologies at the intersection of different fields, for example, technologies for diagnosing diseases using images - a synthesis of medicine and machine learning.

Almost all economic sectors are undergoing digital transformation: work processes are being transferred to a digital format. For example, companies are automating resource and process management using electronic document management and ERP systems. They are using digital technologies such as cloud solutions for data storage, and developing digital skills of personnel.

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